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Features of conducting music classes at school

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Abstract: This article deals with music lessons in secondary schools of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Keywords: school, music, musical and aesthetic culture, child, musical creativity.

The Republic of Uzbekistan has developed a musical and aesthetic culture. Music classes are held in all schools of our country, which are equipped and equipped with visual aids, audio equipment, musical instruments, projectors and televisions.

The lesson of musical culture is considered today as a work of artistic and pedagogical art. The systematic work of musical education in musical and rhythmic activity develops the imagination of children, their creative activity, teaches a conscious attitude to perceived music. This attitude to the perception of music fills the child with joy and opens up a rich world of goodness, light, beauty for the child, as well as teaches creative transformative activity.

Music helps to understand the beauty of the surrounding world, people, animals, various phenomena and pictures of nature, it can also amuse and sadden, you can dance to it, march, act out various scenes, etc. It is not for nothing that the people have the expression "the soul sings". Indeed, listening to music, people's mood rises and fatigue goes away.

The leading principle of the pedagogy of music education, which is relevant at different stages of its development - to interest and captivate schoolchildren with music requires bringing to the first stage those methods of teaching and upbringing that allow students to understand and feel that music is an integral part of their lives, a phenomenon of the world created by man. Immersion in the atmosphere of music, the possibility of plot construction of musical culture, in which the sound of musical fragments, singing, musical and rhythmic exercises, plastic movements follow each other, clinging to one another, flowing and enriching, without letting you relax and stop for a minute. Music is everywhere, in everything, it lives inside the plot and the children. There is no need to force someone to repeat something. The plot as a dramatic core combines the material into one whole at different program levels of the lesson, quarter, half-year. The plot is based on a story created by a teacher, like a didactic fairy tale game. The heroes of songs, musical terms in personified form can live and act in it, events occur prompted by the content of the music and text.

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Here you can rely on popular fairy tale motifs. You can connect the desire and imagination of the children themselves. Fairy tale, fairy-tale images, symbolism are close and understandable to children. Every child lives in a world where everything can talk, think, sing, move and feel. All this allows you to introduce children to the world of music, focusing on the fact that now he is learning to sing, intimate, master the rhythm, the basics of musical literacy, improvisation, etc.

In the process of music lessons, everything happens naturally. But despite this, it is necessary to take into account the psychological characteristics of schoolchildren: instability of attention, the need to change emotional states, rapid fatigue, motor activity, immediacy of experiences, the need for self-expression in a variety of forms.

A music lesson involves the perception and performance of music, as well as musical creativity. This is done mainly in the process of such types of musical activities as listening to music and choral singing. In addition, movements to music, improvisation and playing elementary musical instruments are introduced into the structure of the lesson. All this is used as an effective tool to help students feel and understand music better.

Striving to achieve the main goal - the education of aesthetic feelings - gives the entire structure of the lesson an internal unity. At the same time, the inclusion of various types of musical activities contributes to the general interest of the entire team and each student individually. Students should enjoy communicating with music in the classroom. Only then can its educational function be fully realized.

By saturating the music education program with national and regional material, its users bring the conceptual framework, the "state standard" of music education, closer to the features and tasks of musical work carried out by the region, city, school or even school class.

In accordance with the proposed concept of musical education of schoolchildren, the main task of music lessons at school is to awaken students' interest in artistic music, to teach them to feel, understand, love and appreciate musical art, to enjoy it; to perceive music emotionally positively, feeling the need for systematic communication with it.

Conclusion: Today, when integration processes at school already lead to the fact that the teaching of many school subjects is not complete without art, there is a tendency to carry out education in unity of principles and methods of teaching the basics of science and art.

The modern view of the music lesson increasingly defends the position that the music lesson should firstly be an art lesson. There are more and more supporters of teaching music at school as an art. However, it is precisely in understanding what needs to be done to make a music lesson really an art lesson that there are discrepancies, sometimes expressed in polar opposite points of view.

It is in the education of a living sense of music that the origins of the approach to teaching music as a living figurative art are seen.

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